

Haptemes in (Social-)Haptic Communication Devices

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Abstract. Originating in the deafblind community, social-haptic communication (SHC) augments tactile and spoken language with social, environmental and contextual information through touch messages called haptices which are made up of haptemes – grammar elements based on the way touch is delivered. Currently, haptices must be delivered directly from one person to another, but there are situations when it would be desirable to deliver these remotely through a device. This paper considers whether the concept of haptemes apply to haptic signals delivered through devices, and if so, how we might apply them to the design of such haptic signals. We discuss early experiments with a vibrotactile vest and a single deafblind individual (one of the authors), then discuss how this might be taken forwards more formally in future work.

Keywords: Social-haptic communication, Haptice, Hapteme

1. Social-Haptic Communication

Social-haptic communication (SHC) was developed by Palmer and Lahtinen to convey social, environmental and contextual information to people with dual sensory impairments [1]. SHC augments tactile sign language and speech with touch messages that can be delivered to a person while they are speaking or signing. Lahtinen [2] defines SHC as comprising haptemes (grammar elements – pressure, location, movement) which are combined to form haptices (touch messages, from a simple “yes”/“no” to description of room layouts). SHC has been adopted across the world, and various dictionaries of haptices have developed [2,3]. By definition, SHC takes place between people, but there are times when it would be useful to have haptices delivered through a device, without the need for an interpreter (on a video call, or when interpreters are unavailable). Various devices mimic tactile communication, based on deafblind finger spelling [4] or ProTactile [5]. Most relevant to SHC, SUITCEYES explored the use of vibration motors on the back to deliver “haptograms” based on existing haptices [6]. Trying to recreate the complexities of human touch through a device is currently impossible. Moving directly from a haptice to a haptogram delivered by a device is a straightforward way of sidestepping this problem: focusing on the distinguishability of haptograms, rather than worrying about the subtleties of human touch. This still leaves

the questions: can more nuanced communication be achieved through an electromechanical interface? Can the same grammar be used, or is the grammar of touch through a device necessarily different to the grammar of human touch?

2. Methods

There are many methods of delivering haptic communication: vibrotactile, direct tapping through solenoids, mid-air haptics, thermal feedback or shape-changing devices. Intuitively, it is desirable that haptic signals delivered through devices should be similar to those delivered by hand, to avoid the need to learn a second set of haptic signals. However, each haptic modality is likely to have its own grammar elements, which may be different from the Haptemes delivered in direct human touch. Our goal is to explore the similarities and differences between different haptic interfaces and the haptemes developed by Lahtinen [2]. For this research, we used a bHaptics TactSuit x40, which provides a 5x4 array of vibration motors on the back and front, similar to the grid adopted in the SUITCEYES project. bHaptics provides software that allows users to design and play haptic signals that can have multiple points of interaction, a haptic brush effect to generate apparent motion between points and direct control over the intensity of each motor. There are several haptemes that can be used as variables to construct haptics in human touch: the shape and direction of a movement; its size/length; its speed/duration; the pressure applied; the body location used. With the TactSuit x40, the haptemes available for constructing haptograms are similar, but intensity of vibration replaces pressure, and body location used is limited to the chest or back. As an initial exploration of the approach of this system, we tested it with one of the authors who is deafblind and familiar with SHC. We used the bHaptics Designer to recreate a sequence of haptics, with which the individual was familiar, and explored how they were perceived as we adjusted the “haptemes”. Four example emotional face expression haptics are included in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Example Haptics: (a) Happy; (b) Sad; (c) Angry; (d) Question.

3. Pilot Results

Haptics had to be larger and more exaggerated when delivered through the vest than when delivered by hand. For example, “happy” and “sad” ended up requiring a significant vertical component at their beginning and end in order to differentiate them reliably from a “neutral” expression (a straight horizontal line). The haptic brush effect worked well, particularly on “question” where the curve was reported as being very smooth. “Angry” presented a particular challenge. The first sign we tried attempted to

replicate the haptice used in social-haptic communication (a hand, scratching all five digits backwards and forwards). However, the sensation was described as being too mellow – it didn’t convey the “spikiness” of the finger contact. A more effective version established was to have the four corner motors of the vest pulse on and off quickly to a high intensity, conveying a more “angry” feeling.

4. Further Work

Our preliminary results suggest that to deliver SHC through machine interfaces successfully, it is important to characterise the grammar of these interfaces and how they compare with the haptemes feasible in direct touch. Treating haptices as a shape to be replicated directly is not necessarily the best strategy, but it is undesirable to ask SHC users to learn a whole new set of haptices from scratch to enable communication via machine. Our aim is to determine analogues between the haptemes used in touch and those used by a given machine interface to make translation between the two simpler.

The next step will be to compare two vibrotactile interfaces (the ERM-based bHaptics TactSuit x40; and the voice-coil-based HSD mk.II from Actronika), with direct touch. We will select a set of haptices that utilize the full range of haptemes; explore how these are delivered by expert and novice users of SHC; and then explore how adjusting different parameters of the vibrotactile signals to equate to the touch haptemes affects the perception of the selected haptices.

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